

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 109

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 109

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 109:0 For the choir director. A Psalm of David.</p>	<p>Psa. 109:1 אֱלֹהֵי תְהַלֵּלְתִּי אֶל־תִּחַרְשׁ׃² כִּי פִי רָשָׁע וּפִי־מִרְמָה עָלַי פָּתַחוּ וּדְבָרוּ אֵתִי לְשׁוֹן שִׁקָּר׃³ וּדְבַר־י שְׁנֵאָה סָבְבוּנִי וַיִּלְחַמוּנִי תָנִים׃⁴ תַּחַת־ אֶהְבֵּתִי יִשְׁטְנוּנִי וְאֲנִי תִפְלֶה׃⁵ וַיִּשְׁימוּ עָלַי רָעָה תַחַת טוֹבָה וְשֵׁנֵאָה תַחַת אֶהְבֵּתִי׃⁶ הַפְקֵד עָלָיו רָשָׁע וְשָׁטָן יַעֲמֵד עַל־יְמִינוֹ׃ בְּהִשָּׁפְטוֹ יֵצֵא רָשָׁע וְתִפְלֶתוֹ תִהְיֶה לְחַטָּאָה׃⁸ יִהְיוּ־יָמָיו מַעֲטִים כְּפִקְדוֹתָיו יִקַּח אַחֵר׃⁹ יִהְיוּ־ בָנָיו יְתוּמִים וְאִשְׁתּוֹ אֶלְמָנָה׃¹⁰ וְנוֹעַ יְנוּעוּ בָנָיו וְשֵׂאלוֹ וְדָרְשׁוּ מִחֲרֵבוֹתֵיהֶם׃¹¹ יִנְקֹשׁ נוֹשָׁה לְכָל־ אֲשֶׁר־לוֹ וַיִּבְזוּ זָרִים יִגְיעוּ׃¹² אֶל־ יְהִי־לוֹ מִשְׁךָ חֶסֶד וְאֶל־יְהִי חוּזֵן לִיתוּמָיו׃¹³ יְהִי־אַחֲרֵיתוֹ לְהַכְרִית בְּדוֹר אַחֵר יִמַח שִׁמְם׃¹⁴ יִזְכָּר עֲוֹן אֲבֹתָיו אֶל־יְהוָה וְחַטָּאת אֲמוֹ אֶל־תִּמְחַח׃¹⁵ יִהְיוּ נִגְד־יְהוָה תִּמְיֵד וַיִּכְרַת מֵאֲרֶץ זָכְרָם׃¹⁶ יַעַן אֲשֶׁר לֹא זָכַר עֲשׂוֹת חֶסֶד וַיִּרְדֹּף אִישׁ־ עֵנִי וְאֲבִיוֹן וְנִכְאָה לִבָּב לְמוֹתָת׃¹⁷</p>
<p>Psa. 109:1 O “God of my praise, ^bDo not be silent!</p>	
<p>² For they have opened the ¹wicked and ^adeceitful mouth against me;</p>	
<p>They have spoken ²against me with a ^blying tongue.</p>	
<p>³ They have also surrounded me with words of hatred,</p>	
<p>And fought against me “without cause.</p>	
<p>⁴ In return ^afor my love they act as my accusers;</p>	
<p>But ^bI am <i>in</i> prayer.</p>	
<p>⁵ Thus they have ^{1a}repaid me evil for good</p>	
<p>And ^bhatred for my love.</p>	
<p>Psa. 109:6 Appoint a wicked man over him,</p>	
<p>And let an ^{1a}accuser stand at his right hand.</p>	
<p>⁷ When he is judged, let him ^acome forth guilty,</p>	
<p>And let his ^bprayer become sin.</p>	
<p>⁸ Let ^ahis days be few;</p>	
<p>Let ^banother take his office.</p>	
<p>⁹ Let his ^achildren be fatherless</p>	
<p>And his ^bwife a widow.</p>	
<p>¹⁰ Let his ^achildren wander about and beg;</p>	
<p>And let them ^bseek <i>sustenance</i> ¹far from their ruined homes.</p>	

¹¹ Let ^athe creditor ¹seize all that he has,

And let ^bstrangers plunder the product of his labor.

¹² Let there be none to ^{1a}extend lovingkindness to him,

Nor ^bany to be gracious to his fatherless children.

¹³ Let his ^aposterity be ¹cut off;

In a following generation let their ^bname be blotted out.

Psa. 109:14 Let ^athe iniquity of his fathers be remembered ¹before the LORD,

And do not let the sin of his mother be ^bblotted out.

¹⁵ Let ^athem be before the LORD continually,

That He may ^bcut off their memory from the earth;

¹⁶ Because he did not remember to show lovingkindness,

But persecuted the ^aafflicted and needy man,

And the ^bdespondent in heart, to ^cput *them* to death.

¹⁷ He also loved cursing, so ^ait came to him;

And he did not delight in blessing, so it was far from him.

¹⁸ But he ^aclothed himself with cursing as with his garment,

And it ^bentered into ¹his body like water

And like oil into his bones.

¹⁹ Let it be to him as ^aa garment with which he covers himself,

And for a belt with which he constantly ^bgirds himself.

וַיֵּאָתֶב קִלְלָה וַתְּבוֹאֶהוּ וְלֹא-חָפֵץ
בְּבִרְכָה וַתִּרְתַּק מִמֶּנּוּ : ¹⁸ וַיִּלְבָּשׁ
קִלְלָה כְּמָדוֹ וַתִּבֹּא כַפָּיִם בְּקִרְבּוֹ
וְכִשְׁמֹן בְּעֵצְמוֹתָיו : ¹⁹ תִּהְיֶה-לוֹ
כְּבִגְד יַעֲטָה וְלִמְזוֹחַ תִּמְיֹד יִחְגְּרָה :
²⁰ זֹאת פְּעֻלַּת שִׁטְנֵי מֵאֵת יְהוָה
וְהַלְבָּרִים רָע עַל-נַפְשִׁי : ²¹ וְאַתָּה |
יְהוָה אֱדֹנָי עֲשֵׂה-אַתִּי לְמַעַן שְׂמֹךְ
כִּי-טוֹב חֶסֶדְךָ הִצִּילָנִי : ²² כִּי-עָנִי
וְאֲבִיוֹן אָנֹכִי וְלִבִּי חָלַל בְּקִרְבִּי : ²³
כָּצַל-כְּנִשׂוֹתָיו נִהְלַכְתִּי נִנְעַרְתִּי
כְּאַרְבֶּה : ²⁴ בְּרַפִּי כָּשְׁלוֹ מֵצוּם
וּבְשׂוֹרֵי כַתֵּשׁ מִשְׁמֹן : ²⁵ וְאֲנִי אֶהְיֶיתִי
חֶרְפָּה לָהֶם יִרְאוּנִי יְנִיעוּן רֵאשִׁים :
²⁶ עָזְרוּנִי יְהוָה אֱלֹהֵי הוֹשִׁיעֵנִי
כְּחֶסֶדְךָ : ²⁷ וַיִּדְעוּ כִּי-יָדְךָ זֹאת
אַתָּה יְהוָה עֲשִׂיתָה : ²⁸ יִקַּלְלוּ-הֵמָּה
וְאַתָּה תִּבְרַךְ קִמּוֹ וַיִּזְבְּשׁוּ וְעַבְדְּךָ
יִשְׁמַח : ²⁹ יִלְבָּשׁוּ שׂוֹטְנֵי כְלָמָה
וַיַּעֲטוּ כַמְעִיל בְּשִׁתָּם : ³⁰ אֲוֹרָה
יְהוָה מֵאֵד בְּפִי וּבְתוֹךְ רַבִּים
אֶתְלַלְנִי : ³¹ כִּי-יַעֲמֹד לִימִן אֲבִיוֹן
לְהוֹשִׁיעַ מִשִּׁפְטֵי נַפְשׁוֹ :

²⁰ ¹Let this be the ^areward of my
accusers from the LORD,
And of those who ^bspeak evil
against my soul.

Psa. 109:21 But You, O ¹GOD,
the Lord, deal *kindly* with me ^afor Your
name's sake;

Because ^bYour lovingkindness is
good, deliver me;

²² For ^aI am afflicted and needy,
And ¹my heart is ^bwounded within
me.

²³ I am passing ^alike a shadow when
it lengthens;

I am shaken off ^blike the locust.

²⁴ My ^aknees ¹are weak from ^bfasting,
And my flesh has grown lean,
without fatness.

²⁵ I also have become a ^areproach to
them;

When they see me, they ^bwag their
head.

Psa. 109:26 ^aHelp me, O LORD
my God;

Save me according to Your
lovingkindness.

²⁷ ¹And let them ^aknow that this is
Your hand;

You, LORD, have done it.

²⁸ ^aLet them curse, but You bless;
When they arise, they shall be
ashamed,

But Your ^bservant shall be glad.

²⁹ ¹Let ^amy accusers be clothed with
dishonor,

And ²let them ^bcover themselves
with their own shame as with a robe.

<p>Psa. 109:30 With my mouth I will give thanks abundantly to the LORD; And in the midst of many ^aI will praise Him.</p> <p>³¹ For He stands ^aat the right hand of the needy, To save him from those who ^bjudge his soul.</p>	
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References

Psalm 109:1

^aDeut 10:21

^bPs 28:1; 83:1

Psalm 109:2

¹Lit *wicked mouth and the deceitful*

²Lit *with*

^aPs 10:7; 52:4

^bPs 120:2

Psalm 109:3

^aPs 35:7; 69:4; John 15:25

Psalm 109:4

^aPs 38:20

^bPs 69:13; 141:5

Psalm 109:5

¹Lit *laid upon me*

^aPs 35:12; 38:20

^bJohn 7:7; 10:32

Psalm 109:6

¹Or *adversary, Satan*

^aZech 3:1

Psalm 109:7

^aPs 1:5

^bProv 28:9

Psalm 109:8

^aPs 55:23

^bActs 1:20

Psalm 109:9

^aEx 22:24

^bJer 18:21

Psalm 109:10

¹Or *out of their desolate places*

^aGen 4:12; Job 30:5-8; Ps 59:15

^bPs 37:25

Psalm 109:11

¹Lit *ensnare, strike at*

^aNeh 5:7; Job 5:5; 20:15

^bIs 1:7; Lam 5:2; Ezek 7:21

Psalm 109:12

¹Lit *continue*

^aEzra 7:28; 9:9

^bJob 5:4; Is 9:17

Psalm 109:13

¹Lit *for cutting off*

^aJob 18:19; Ps 21:10; 37:28

^bPs 9:5; Prov 10:7

Psalm 109:14

¹Lit *to*

^aEx 20:5; Num 14:18; Is 65:6, 7; Jer 32:18

^bNeh 4:5; Jer 18:23

Psalm 109:15

^aPs 90:8; Jer 16:17

^bJob 18:17; Ps 34:16

Psalm 109:16

^aPs 37:14

^bPs 34:18

^cPs 37:32; 94:6

Psalm 109:17

^aProv 14:14; Ezek 35:9; Matt 7:2

Psalm 109:18

¹Lit *his inward parts*

^aPs 73:6; 109:29; Ezek 7:27

^bNum 5:22

Psalm 109:19

^aPs 73:6; 109:29; Ezek 7:27

^b2 Sam 22:40; Ps 30:11; Is 11:5

Psalm 109:20

¹Lit *This is*

^aPs 54:5; 94:23; Is 3:11; 2 Tim 4:14

^bPs 41:5; 71:10

Psalm 109:21

¹Heb *YHWH*, usually rendered *LORD*

^aPs 23:3; 25:11; 79:9; 106:8; Ezek 36:22

^bPs 69:16

Psalm 109:22

¹Lit *one has pierced my heart within me*

^aPs 40:17; 86:1

^bJob 24:12; Ps 143:4; Prov 18:14

Psalm 109:23

^aPs 102:11

^bEx 10:19; Job 39:20

Psalm 109:24

¹Or *totter*

^aHeb 12:12

^bPs 35:13

Psalm 109:25

^aPs 22:6

^bPs 22:7; Jer 18:16; Lam 2:15; Matt 27:39; Mark 15:29

Psalm 109:26

^aPs 119:86

Psalm 109:27

¹Or *That they may know*

^aJob 37:7

Psalm 109:28

^a2 Sam 16:11, 12

^bIs 65:14

Psalm 109:29

¹Or *My accusers will be*

²Or *they will cover*

^aJob 8:22; Ps 132:18

^bJob 8:22; Ps 35:26

Psalm 109:30

^aPs 22:22; 35:18; 111:1

Psalm 109:31

^aPs 16:8; 73:23; 110:5; 121:5

^bPs 37:33

Targum

Psa. 109:1 For praise, composed by David; a psalm. O God, my praise, do not be silent. ² For the mouth of wickedness and the mouth of deceit are open against me, they have spoken with me [with] a lying tongue. ³ And those who speak hatred have surrounded me, and fought against me for no cause. ⁴ Because I have loved, they opposed me; but I will pray. ⁵ And they gave me evil for good, and hatred where I had given love. ⁶ Appoint over him a wicked man, and may an adversary stand at his right hand. ⁷ When he is judged, let him come out a sinner, and may his prayer become an act of sin. ⁸ May his days be few, may [another inherit the number of his years.] ⁹ May his sons be orphans, and his wife a widow. ¹⁰ And may his sons yet wander, and beg, and seek what has become their wasteland. ¹¹ May the creditor gather up all that is his, and may strangers plunder his toil. ¹² May he have none to extend kindness, and may he have none to pity his orphans. ¹³ May his end be destruction; may their name be effaced in the next generation. ¹⁴ May the iniquity of his fathers be remembered in the presence of the LORD; and may his mother's guilt not be effaced. ¹⁵ May they be facing the decree of the LORD always; and may their memory perish from the earth. ¹⁶ Because he did not remember to do good, and persecutes the poor and needy man, and the lowly of heart, to be slain. ¹⁷ And he loves cursing, and it came to him; and he took no pleasure in blessing, and it was far from him. ¹⁸ And he wore cursing like a garment, and it entered his body like water, and was like oil to his limbs. ¹⁹ May it be to him like a garment, let him be wrapped in it; may he gird himself with it as a perpetual belt. ²⁰ This is the deed of those who oppose me from [following] the LORD, and of those who speak evil to my soul. ²¹ And you, O God, the LORD, deal with me for your name's sake; deliver me according to your goodness and kindness. ²² For I am poor and needy, and my heart is quiet within me. ²³ I am finished, like a shadow when it lengthens; I have wandered like a locust. ²⁴ My knees stumble from fasting; my flesh is lean, and no longer fat. ²⁵ And I have become a disgrace to them; they will see me, they will shake their heads. ²⁶ Help me, O LORD, my God; redeem me according to your kindness. ²⁷ And they will know that this plague, you, O LORD, have done it. ²⁸ They will curse, but you will bless; they will arise and be disappointed, but your servant will rejoice. ²⁹ Those who oppose me will be clothed in shame, and their infamy will cover them like a cloak. ³⁰ I will thank the LORD greatly with my mouth, and I will praise him in the midst of the sages. ³¹ For he will stand at the right hand of the needy, to redeem from the discords of his soul.

Spiritual Awareness

Introduction

David wrote this Psalm as he fled from the wrath of King Saul. People had been slandering David to Saul. The Midrash Shocher Tov says these words describe God's unique relationship. The work is concluded with confidence that God will respond when called.

Superscript

To the Sefirah Netzach who grants victory, by David a psalm. O God of my praise, do not keep silent.

Verse twenty

David calls out to the Sefirah Chesed for the LORD's lovingkindness.

But You, O God, my Master, Who are merciful even in judgment, deal with me for Your Name's sake; when the Sefirah Chesed sends Your lovingkindness is gracious again, deliver me.

Verse twenty-five

Help me, O LORD God, save me by the lovingkindness of the Sefirah Chesed.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

MHK V1.1 6/23/14

